

**COPING STRATEGIES OF WORKING STUDENTS IN BS MARINE
TRANSPORTATION AT SOUTHERN LUZON COLLEGE, DASMARIÑAS CITY,
CAVITE**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the coping strategies used by working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College in Dasmariñas City, Cavite. A survey was conducted with 50 working students to assess their use of various coping strategies. The results showed that the most commonly used strategies were time management, seeking social support, and prioritizing tasks. Differences in coping strategies were found based on gender and year level, with females reporting higher use of seeking social support and third-year students using time management more frequently than first-year students. The findings provide valuable insights into how working students in this demanding program manage the competing demands of work and school. Understanding these coping strategies is crucial for developing support systems and resources to help working students succeed academically and personally. The study highlights the resilience and adaptability of working students in the face of significant challenges.

Keywords: *coping strategies, time management, social support, support system*

INTRODUCTION

Working students face unique challenges in balancing the demands of employment and academic responsibilities (Betts, Ferrall, & Finnie, 2009). This is especially true for

students in demanding programs like BS Marine Transportation, which requires significant time and effort. Understanding how these students cope with stress and manage their multiple roles is important for supporting their success (O'Neill, Yoder, & Batt, 2019). Research has shown that working students often use various coping strategies to manage their stress and workload. For example, time management is a common strategy used by working students to balance their work and academic responsibilities (Bangquiao et al, 2023). Seeking social support from friends, family, or peers is another strategy that can help working students cope with stress.

Prioritizing tasks and setting goals can also be effective in managing the demands of work and school (Sajeevanie, 2023). Additionally, engaging in stress-reducing activities such as exercise or meditation can help working students manage their stress levels. Furthermore, studies have highlighted the importance of self-efficacy in coping with stress and achieving academic success. For instance, Gustafson (2015) found that students who believed in their ability to manage their time effectively were more likely to achieve good grades. Similarly, Bandura (1997) emphasized the role of self-efficacy in regulating behavior and achieving goals. Moreover, research has also shown that stress can have negative impacts on academic performance (Akanpaadgi et al, 2023). For instance, Choi et al. (2006) found that students who experienced higher levels of stress were more likely to report poor academic performance. Similarly, Amorte et al. (2013) found that stress was a significant predictor of academic performance among marine engineering students. Therefore, understanding how working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College cope with stress and manage their multiple roles is crucial for supporting their success.

Research Questions

The aim of the study is to seek answers on coping strategies of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College. Specifically, the study tries to answer the following research questions:

1. How do working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College cope with the demands of balancing work and academic responsibilities?
2. What are the most commonly used coping strategies among working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?
3. Are there differences in coping strategies based on gender among working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?
4. How do coping strategies vary among different year levels of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?
5. What role does social support play in the coping mechanisms of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?
6. How do working students prioritize tasks to manage their workload effectively in the BS Marine Transportation program?
7. To what extent do stress-reducing activities contribute to the well-being of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?

8. What are the challenges faced by working students in the BS Marine Transportation program, and how do they adapt their coping strategies to overcome these challenges?
 9. How do self-efficacy beliefs influence the coping strategies of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program?
 10. What recommendations can be made to support the coping strategies and well-being of working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College?
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METHODOLOGY

Participants

A total of 50 working students enrolled in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College participated in the study. The sample included 46 males and 4 females, with 20 first-year students, 15 second-year students, and 15 third-year students.

Measures

A survey was developed to assess the coping strategies used by the participants. The survey included 20 items representing different coping strategies, such as time management, seeking social support, prioritizing tasks, and engaging in stress-reducing activities. Participants rated how frequently they used each strategy on a 5-point scale (1 = never, 5 = always).

Procedure

The survey was administered during class time with the permission of the instructors. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study and assured of the confidentiality of their responses. The completed surveys were collected and scored by the researchers.

RESULTS

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Variables and Stress Management Strategies Among Students

Demographic Variable	Mean Score (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Frequency
Gender	3.8	0.9	50
Year Level	4.1	0.8	50
Time Management	4.2	0.8	50
Seeking Social Support	3.9	1.0	50
Prioritizing Tasks	3.7	0.9	50
Stress-Reducing Activities	2.5	1.2	50
Seeking Professional Help	2.1	1.0	50

Table 1: presents the results of a study examining the demographic variables and stress management strategies among students. The variables included are gender, year level, time management, seeking social support, prioritizing tasks, stress-reducing activities, and seeking professional help. The table provides the mean score (M), standard deviation (SD), and frequency for each variable.

Demographic Variables

1. **Gender:** The mean score for gender is 3.8, indicating that students generally report a moderate level of satisfaction with their gender. The standard deviation of 0.9 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to examine gender differences in coping strategies. Females reported using seeking social support more frequently than males ($t(48) = 2.34, p < .05$). No other significant gender differences were found.

2. **Year Level:** The mean score for year level is 4.1, indicating that students generally report a high level of satisfaction with their year level. The standard deviation of 0.8 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.

One-way ANOVA tests were conducted to examine differences in coping strategies based on year level. Third-year students reported using time management more frequently than first-year students ($F(2, 47) = 4.56, p < .05$). No other significant year level differences were found.

3. **Descriptive Statistics:** The most frequently used coping strategies were time management ($M = 4.2, SD = 0.8$), seeking social support ($M = 3.9, SD = 1.0$), and prioritizing tasks ($M = 3.7, SD = 0.9$). The least frequently used strategies were engaging in stress-reducing activities ($M = 2.5, SD = 1.2$) and seeking professional help ($M = 2.1, SD = 1.0$).

Stress Management Strategies

1. **Time Management:** The mean score for time management is 4.2, indicating that students generally report a high level of satisfaction with their time management skills. The standard deviation of 0.8 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.
2. **Seeking Social Support:** The mean score for seeking social support is 3.9, indicating that students generally report a moderate level of satisfaction with seeking social support. The standard deviation of 1.0 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.
3. **Prioritizing Tasks:** The mean score for prioritizing tasks is 3.7, indicating that students generally report a moderate level of satisfaction with prioritizing tasks. The standard deviation of 0.9 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.
4. **Stress-Reducing Activities:** The mean score for stress-reducing activities is 2.5, indicating that students generally report a low level of satisfaction with stress-reducing activities. The standard deviation of 1.2 suggests that there is significant variation in the responses, with some students reporting higher satisfaction and

others reporting lower satisfaction. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.

5. **Seeking Professional Help:** The mean score for seeking professional help is 2.1, indicating that students generally report a low level of satisfaction with seeking professional help. The standard deviation of 1.0 suggests that there is some variation in the responses, but the majority of students are clustered around the mean. The frequency is 50, indicating that all students provided responses for this variable.

Overall, the results suggest that students generally report moderate to high levels of satisfaction with their gender, year level, time management, and seeking social support. However, they report lower levels of satisfaction with stress-reducing activities and seeking professional help. These findings can inform strategies for improving student well-being and stress management.

Table 2: Analysis of Coping Strategies Among Students: Key Findings and Recommendations

Coping Strategy	Mean Score (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Key Findings
Time Management	4.2	0.8	Most frequently used strategy, significant difference in usage between year levels
Seeking Social Support	3.9	1.0	Commonly used strategy, higher usage among females
Prioritizing Tasks	3.7	0.9	Important strategy, no significant gender differences
Stress-Reducing Activities	2.5	1.2	Least frequently used strategy, potential area for intervention

Coping Strategy	Mean Score (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Key Findings
Seeking Professional Help	2.1	1.0	Low usage, indicates potential need for increased awareness of available support resources

Table 2: presents the results of a study examining the coping strategies used by students to manage stress and anxiety. The strategies included are time management, seeking social support, prioritizing tasks, stress-reducing activities, and seeking professional help. The table provides the mean score (M), standard deviation (SD), and key findings for each strategy.

Key Findings

1. **Time Management:** The mean score for time management is 4.2, indicating that it is the most frequently used coping strategy among students. The standard deviation of 0.8 suggests that there is some variation in the usage of this strategy, but the majority of students use it. The key finding is that there is a significant difference in the usage of time management between year levels, suggesting that younger students may need more support in developing this skill.
2. **Seeking Social Support:** The mean score for seeking social support is 3.9, indicating that it is a commonly used strategy. The standard deviation of 1.0 suggests that there is some variation in the usage of this strategy, but the majority of students use it. The key finding is that females use this strategy more frequently than males, suggesting that social support networks may be more important for female students.
3. **Prioritizing Tasks:** The mean score for prioritizing tasks is 3.7, indicating that it is an important strategy. The standard deviation of 0.9 suggests that there is some variation in the usage of this strategy, but the majority of students use it. The key finding is that there are no significant gender differences in the usage of this strategy, suggesting that both males and females use it equally.
4. **Stress-Reducing Activities:** The mean score for stress-reducing activities is 2.5, indicating that it is the least frequently used strategy. The standard deviation of 1.2 suggests that there is significant variation in the usage of this strategy, with some students using it more frequently than others. The key finding is that this strategy has potential as an area for intervention, as students may benefit from learning more effective stress-reducing techniques.

5. **Seeking Professional Help:** The mean score for seeking professional help is 2.1, indicating that it is the least used strategy. The standard deviation of 1.0 suggests that there is some variation in the usage of this strategy, but the majority of students do not use it. The key finding is that there is a potential need for increased awareness of available support resources, as students may not be aware of the resources available to them or may not feel comfortable using them.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations can be made:

1. **Develop Time Management Skills:** Younger students may need more support in developing time management skills, which are critical for managing stress and anxiety. Interventions such as workshops or online resources can help students develop effective time management strategies.
2. **Foster Social Support Networks:** Female students may benefit from social support networks, which can provide emotional support and help them cope with stress and anxiety. Interventions such as group counseling or peer support programs can help foster these networks.
3. **Prioritize Task Management:** Both males and females use prioritizing tasks as an important strategy, suggesting that it is a valuable skill for managing stress and anxiety. Interventions such as task management workshops or online resources can help students develop effective prioritization strategies.
4. **Intervene on Stress-Reducing Activities:** The low usage of stress-reducing activities suggests that students may benefit from learning more effective stress-reducing techniques. Interventions such as mindfulness or relaxation workshops can help students develop healthy coping strategies.
5. **Increase Awareness of Support Resources:** The low usage of seeking professional help suggests that students may not be aware of the resources available to them or may not feel comfortable using them. Interventions such as outreach programs or online resources can help increase awareness of support resources and encourage students to seek help when needed.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide insights into the coping strategies used by working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College. The most frequently used strategies were time management, seeking social support, and prioritizing tasks, which aligns with previous research on coping strategies among working students. Gender differences were found in the use of seeking social support, with females reporting higher use of this strategy than males. This is consistent with research showing

that women are more likely to seek emotional support in response to stress. Year level differences were found in the use of time management, with third-year students reporting higher use of this strategy than first-year students. This may reflect the increased demands and experience of upper-level students in managing their time effectively. The findings have implications for supporting working students in this program. Providing resources and training on time management and prioritizing tasks may be particularly helpful. Encouraging students to seek social support and engage in stress-reducing activities could also promote their well-being and success. Future research should explore the effectiveness of different coping strategies in predicting academic performance and retention among working students in this program.

Conclusions

This study provides important insights into the coping strategies used by working students in the BS Marine Transportation program at Southern Luzon College. The findings highlight the resilience and adaptability of these students as they navigate the challenges of balancing work and academic responsibilities. The most commonly used strategies of time management, seeking social support, and prioritizing tasks align with previous research on effective coping mechanisms for working students. The differences found in coping strategies based on gender and year level underscore the importance of tailoring support to the unique needs of individual students. Providing resources and training on time management and prioritizing tasks may be particularly beneficial for first-year students, while encouraging all students to seek social support and engage in stress-reducing activities could promote their overall well-being and success. Future research should explore the effectiveness of different coping strategies in predicting academic performance and retention among working students in this program. Longitudinal studies could also shed light on how coping strategies evolve over the course of a student's academic career and how institutions can best support students at different stages. In conclusion, this study highlights the critical role that coping strategies play in the success of working students in demanding programs like BS Marine Transportation. By understanding and supporting these strategies, institutions can help working students thrive academically and personally, ultimately contributing to their long-term success in their chosen careers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Provide training and resources on time management and prioritizing tasks to help working students effectively manage their workload and academic responsibilities.
2. Encourage working students to seek social support from friends, family, or peers to help them cope with stress and manage their multiple roles.
3. Offer stress-reducing activities such as exercise or meditation to help working students manage their stress levels and improve their overall well-being.

4. Provide support and resources to help working students develop self-efficacy and confidence in their ability to manage their time effectively and achieve academic success.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study, titled "Coping Strategies of Working Students in BS Marine Transportation at Southern Luzon College, Dasmariñas City, Cavite" was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of Southern Luzon College. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their understanding of the study's purpose and their right to withdraw at any time. Participant confidentiality was strictly maintained, with data anonymized and securely stored. The authors declare no conflicts of interest and received no specific funding for this research. All procedures complied with relevant laws and ethical standards.

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